

Sorry about this shabby looking paper

15, St Johns Street,
Oxford.

11/2/72.

*Congratulations you a little you
to be ~~lectures~~ giving the
Reckitt lectures - what will
you do in your 60!*

Dear Karl,

Thank ~~you~~ very much for your letter! I am writing a peice to include both Sirjan and D.D. I ~~just~~ ^{ve} heard that I can include (inshallah!) a photo of D.D. I suppose that the best one is to illustrate again the D.D. room of pots (D.D. 4.) on the grounds that not many people bother to read the survey of excavations in Iran. Does that sound reasonable? After long adventures the print which was illustrated ended up with me in Iran- but it is still being shipped back to England now. Do you have another print available? or do you think something ~~else~~ else should go in? In any case if you can manage something (I'm supposed to produce it by the middle of ^{Month} ~~Feb~~) I'd be most grateful.

Some of the D.D. drawings are still undergoing surgery at Oxford beside the sherds-- to be fair to the artist they are very difficult peices but it is just too hard for me to illustrate "flowing spirals" with drawings that make them look like sick zigzags!!so I am still playing with them.

Did you get a whole D.D. painted pot in the 1971 division? if you did I'd appreciate when you get a chance having it photographed together with the 1970 whole painted pot from DD4 (in December it was on top of the large cabinet to the right of the lab as you enter in splendour beside one of your fine Chinese Neolithic pots). It would clearly be most economical in publication to have them both on one print (black and white and colour slide too please)

Could you get at my expense a B and W and colour slide of the 2 painted pots the Museum has from Istakhr. They are both in the Near Eastern Room. one is on a display to the right of the door, the other is in case 9. Martha could easily find them, and if it is difficult to get a photo done she could easily take a snappy crappy shot for me. I'd half like to show a slide of them at the Oxford Congress if that is O.K. with you.

I've managed to complete ten pages of ~~the~~ the thesis in the last three days. I'm eating drinking and sleeping it,so it is ploughing on.

My best wishes to Marty and everyone at Harvard.

*greetin
Thanks you Fields ~~adviser~~ + your close
on the Sardinia ~~roads~~.*

(Gift of the Porter Museum)

Andy

P.S. Confidentially, as a member of that group I can tell you that I am being asked to give the Reckitt Lectures at the British Academy in 1973. I am honored by this ~~unannounced~~ privilege. But until I find them formally its best to keep absolutely mum.